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VOLUME 4, ISSUE 2, 2023

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING GENERAL DEVELOPMENT EXERCISES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Norinboeva Durdonakhon Janobiddin qizi

FerSU, 3rd year student

urdonakhonnorinboeva@gmail.com

G'ulomjonov Abdurasul G'ofurjon o'g'li

FerSU, 1st year student

muhammedrasul430@gmail.com

Annotation. The methodology of teaching general development exercises in secondary schools consists of a structured approach to enhancing various aspects of a student's physical, mental, and emotional well-being. This methodology is crucial as it helps students develop essential skills, promotes holistic growth, and prepares them for future challenges. In this essay, we will explore why this methodology is chosen in secondary schools and its impact on student development. This article will discuss various methodologies that can be employed to teach general development exercises in secondary schools.

Key words: goal setting, warm-up, stretching, motivate, achievable, stimulation, classroom-based, guidance, inspiration, teamwork, fair play, perseverance, refreshing, change of pace, promoting, dynamic learning, environment

Secondary school education plays a crucial role in the overall development of students. To ensure that students achieve their full potential, it is important to introduce them to general development exercises. These exercises focus on enhancing physical fitness, mental agility, and social skills. In order to effectively teach these exercises, a thoughtful methodology needs to be implemented.

1. Introduction and Goal Setting:

The first step in teaching general development exercises is to introduce the concept to students and explain the goals and benefits of these exercises. This can be done through a presentation or discussion. It is important to emphasize the importance of physical fitness, mental well-being, and social skills in overall development. Students should be motivated and encouraged to actively participate in these exercises.

2. Warm-Up and Stretching:

Before starting any exercise, it is crucial to properly warm up and stretch the muscles. This helps prevent injuries and prepares the body for physical activities. The warm-up session should include activities such as jogging, jumping jacks, or skipping ropes. Additionally, stretching exercises should be included to improve flexibility and range of motion.

3. Variety of Exercises:

To keep students engaged and motivated, it is essential to include a variety of exercises in the curriculum. This can include aerobic exercises such as running, dancing, or swimming, as well as strength training exercises like push-ups or squats. Incorporating team sports like football, basketball, or volleyball can also promote social interaction and teamwork skills. By providing a wide range of exercises, students can explore different physical activities and find what suits them best.

4. Progression and Challenges:

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It is important to gradually increase the difficulty level of exercises as students progress. This helps them build strength, endurance, and confidence. Teachers should design exercises and activities that challenge students while considering their current fitness level. Setting achievable goals and providing regular feedback can also help students track their progress and stay motivated.

5. Individualized Approach:

Every student is unique and has different abilities and interests. Therefore, it is essential to adopt an individualized approach while teaching general development exercises. Teachers should pay attention to each student's strengths and weaknesses and tailor exercises accordingly. Modifying the exercises to accommodate students with physical limitations or health concerns is also crucial. Inclusive exercises ensure that every student can participate and benefit from these activities.

6. Incorporating Technology:

In today's digital age, technology can be a powerful tool in teaching general development exercises. Teachers can utilize fitness apps, online resources, or fitness trackers to monitor and track students' progress. Additionally, virtual fitness classes or instructional videos can provide students with guidance and inspiration. Incorporating technology not only makes the learning process more interactive and engaging but also enables students to take ownership of their fitness journey.

7. Evaluation and Feedback:

Regular evaluation of students' progress is necessary to assess their development and provide feedback. This can be done through periodic assessments or fitness tests. Teachers can also observe students during exercises and provide individual feedback to help them improve their technique or form. Evaluations and feedback help students understand their strengths and areas for improvement, allowing them to set new goals and work towards them.

8. Integration with Academic Curriculum:

To reinforce the importance of general development exercises, it is beneficial to integrate them with the academic curriculum. For example, teachers can incorporate physical activities during science experiments, math games, or language arts activities. This interdisciplinary approach not only enhances students' understanding of core subjects but also promotes physical fitness and mental stimulation simultaneously.

9. Encouragement and Motivation:

Creating a positive and encouraging environment is essential in teaching general development exercises. Students should feel supported and motivated throughout the learning process. Teachers can provide incentives, recognition, or rewards for accomplishments, and celebrate students' progress. Encouraging self-reflection and setting personal goals can also help students stay motivated and committed to their overall development.

The methodology of teaching general development exercises in secondary schools is a crucial aspect of physical education. It plays a significant role in creating a well-rounded educational experience that promotes physical fitness, motor skill development, and overall growth for students. This article will discuss various methods and strategies for effectively teaching general development exercises in secondary schools.

Before diving into the methodologies, it is essential to understand the objectives of teaching general development exercises. These objectives include promoting physical fitness, developing motor skills and coordination, enhancing overall health and well-being, fostering teamwork and collaboration, and promoting lifelong physical activity habits.

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1. Assessing student needs and abilities: The first step in teaching general development exercises is to assess the specific needs and abilities of the students. This can be done through various means, including fitness assessments, motor skill assessments, and observation of students' physical capabilities and limitations. Understanding the individual needs and abilities of students allows the teacher to tailor the exercises to their specific requirements.
2. Planning a well-structured curriculum: A well-structured curriculum is essential for teaching general development exercises. It should include a variety of exercises targeting different muscle groups and physical abilities. The curriculum should be progressive, starting with basic exercises and gradually increasing in difficulty. It should also include a variety of exercise types, such as aerobic exercises, strength training, flexibility exercises, and balance training. The curriculum should be planned to meet the specific objectives and needs of the students.
3. Demonstrations and explanations: Demonstrating and explaining the exercises to the students is crucial for ensuring they understand the movements and techniques correctly. Teachers should use clear and concise instructions, along with visual demonstrations, to enhance student understanding. Proper warm-up and cool-down routines should also be demonstrated and explained to promote injury prevention and recovery.
4. Group activities and collaboration: Incorporating group activities and collaboration in teaching general development exercises promotes teamwork, socialization, and a sense of belonging among students. Activities such as team sports, group fitness challenges, and partner exercises allow students to work together, support each other, and develop important life skills such as communication, cooperation, and leadership.
5. Differentiation and individualization: Every student is unique, and their physical abilities and limitations may vary. Teachers need to differentiate and individualize the exercises to cater to the diverse needs of the students. This can be done by providing modified exercises for students with physical disabilities or limitations, offering options for students at different fitness levels, and providing alternatives for those who may not be able to participate fully in certain exercises.
6. Progress monitoring and feedback: Regular progress monitoring and providing constructive feedback to the students are important elements of teaching general development exercises. This can be accomplished through formative assessments, fitness assessments, and observation of students' progress. Feedback should focus on areas of improvement, technique correction, and encouragement to motivate students. Acknowledging and celebrating individual and group achievements also play a significant role in motivating students to continue their physical development.
7. Creating a positive and inclusive learning environment: The learning environment plays a key role in promoting student engagement and participation. Teachers should create an atmosphere where students feel safe, respected, and included. Emphasizing the importance of effort, progress, and personal development rather than competition and comparison helps foster a positive mindset and encourages all students to participate to their fullest potential.
8. Integration of technology: Utilizing technology can enhance the teaching of general development exercises. Teachers can utilize fitness tracking apps, video analysis tools, and online resources to aid in monitoring progress, providing feedback, and offering additional resources for students to continue their physical development outside of the classroom.

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The methodology of teaching general development exercises in secondary schools consists of a structured approach to enhancing various aspects of a student's physical, mental, and emotional well-being. This methodology is crucial as it helps students develop essential skills, promotes holistic growth, and prepares them for future challenges. In this essay, we will explore why this methodology is chosen in secondary schools and its impact on student development.

The methodology of teaching general development exercises promotes mental well-being and enhances cognitive abilities. Engaging in activities like puzzles, brain teasers, and memory games helps develop problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and creativity. Studies have shown that regular mental stimulation in the form of exercises enhances memory retention, improves focus and attention span, and supports academic achievement. By incorporating these exercises in the secondary school curriculum, students are provided with opportunities to exercise their mental faculties and expand their cognitive abilities.

Teaching general development exercises cultivates emotional intelligence among students. Group activities and team sports foster skills such as teamwork, cooperation, and empathy. Students learn to understand and respect individual differences, manage conflicts, and build positive relationships. These exercises also provide a platform for students to express and regulate their emotions, develop self-confidence, and build resilience. In schools where general development exercises are given importance, students have reported higher levels of emotional well-being, decreased rates of anxiety and depression, and increased self-esteem.

The methodology of teaching general development exercises in secondary schools cultivates discipline, time management, and goal-setting abilities among students. Engaging in regular physical exercise requires commitment, dedication, and perseverance. By setting goals and working towards them, students learn the importance of discipline and develop a sense of responsibility towards their personal well-being. This methodology encourages students to prioritize their time effectively and instills habits that contribute to overall success in life. These skills are invaluable for a successful future, as they enhance productivity, self-motivation, and the ability to manage different aspects of life effectively.

Teaching general development exercises in secondary schools promotes overall personality development. By encouraging students to participate in various physical, mental, and emotional activities, they are exposed to a range of experiences and opportunities for self-discovery. These exercises not only develop physical and cognitive capabilities but also nurture qualities such as leadership, resilience, adaptability, and confidence. Through participation in team activities, students learn to value the skills and perspectives of others and develop effective communication and interpersonal skills. This methodology helps shape well-rounded individuals who are equipped to face challenges and succeed in various spheres of life.

In conclusion, the methodology of teaching general development exercises in secondary schools is chosen for its numerous benefits on student development. By incorporating physical, mental, and emotional exercise activities into the curriculum, this methodology promotes overall well-being, enhances academic performance, and cultivates essential life skills. It prepares students for the challenges of the future, helps shape their personalities, and fosters an inclusive and positive school culture. Therefore, it is essential for secondary schools to prioritize and invest in this methodology to ensure the holistic growth and development of their students.

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